

Evaluation of General Class of Beta Integrals Involving Certain Particular Functions

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Abstract

In this paper general class of Beta integrals is considered for particular function $\phi(t), \psi(t)$ and $f(t)$. This class is further used to evaluate certain integrals for some special functions. The class of integrals studied in this paper is integral involving the product of several exponential functions and Gauss's hypergeometric function. As the application of this general integral some integrals for some particular functions are derived.

Keywords Beta Function, Gamma Function, Exponential Functions, Gauss's Hypergeometric Function, Extended Beta Function, Generalized Hypergeometric Function, Hurwitz-Lerch zeta Function..

Introduction

The well-known Gamma and Beta function are defined and represented by following integrals.[10]

$$\Gamma(\alpha) = \int_0^{\infty} t^{\alpha-1} e^{-t} dt \quad (1.1)$$

And

$$B(\alpha, \beta) = \int_0^{\infty} t^{\alpha-1} (1-t)^{\beta-1} dt ; \operatorname{Re}(\alpha) > 0, \operatorname{Re}(\beta) > 0 \quad (1.2)$$

Choudhary et. al. [1][2] studied and extended these function to the entire complex plane by inserting the

regularization factors $\exp\left(\frac{-A}{t}\right)$ and $\exp\left(\frac{-A}{t(1-t)}\right)$ in the integrands. They studied the following extended form of (1.1) and (1.2) respectively:

$$\Gamma_A(\alpha) = \int_0^{\infty} t^{\alpha-1} \exp\left(t - \frac{A}{t}\right) dt, \quad \text{Re}(A) > 0 \quad (1.3)$$

$$B(\alpha, \beta; A) = \int_0^{\infty} t^{\alpha-1} (1-t)^{\beta-1} \exp\left(\frac{-A}{t(1-t)}\right) dt, \quad \text{Re}(A) > 0 \quad (1.4)$$

These forms of Beta integral are further unified by the following general integrals.[3]

$$I_{\alpha, \beta} [f(t)] = \int_0^1 t^{\alpha-1} (1-t)^{\beta-1} f(t) dt, \quad \text{Re}(\alpha) > 0, \text{Re}(\beta) > 0 \quad (1.5)$$

And[5, p.1995, eq.(2.1)]

$$I_{A, \alpha, \beta, \gamma; a, b} [\phi(t), \psi(t)] = \frac{1}{B(\alpha, \beta)} \int_a^b (t-a)^{\alpha-1} (b-t)^{\beta-1} [\phi(t)]^{\gamma} \exp[-A\psi(t)] dt; \quad (1.6)$$

$$\{\text{Re}(\alpha) > 0, \text{Re}(\beta) > 0, \text{Re}(A)\} > 0$$

Where $\phi(t)$, $\psi(t)$ and $f(t)$ are particular functions and $\phi(t) \neq 0$, $a < t < b$, $a \neq b$

Motivated by certain series integral representations of Hurwitz-Zeta function $\zeta(z, a)$ and Hurwitz Lerch zeta function $\phi(z, s, a)$ ([6][7]) very recently. Jaimini and Sharma [4] studied the extended beta function $B(\alpha, \beta; A)$ by the following general series integral representation.

$$B(\alpha, \beta; A) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(\lambda)_k}{k!} \int_0^1 t^{\alpha-1} (1-t)^{\beta-1} \exp[-(A+kp)\psi(t)] \cdot [1 - \exp(-p\psi(t))]^{\lambda} dt \quad (1.7)$$

$$\text{Where } \psi(t) = \frac{1}{t(1-t)}$$

On summing the series in (1.7) and using binomial expansion it reduce to the original definition in (1.4).

Objective of study

We have studied general class of Beta integrals for particular functions in. This class is used to evaluate certain integrals for some special functions by assigning the different-different forms of the functions. Various known and new simpler integral formulae are obtained from our main results. As the application of these simpler results many interesting consequences are derived. The methodology and technique that we have used in this paper to obtain the results can be further extended for more general new functions. The young researchers can use our finding to develop new study.

Review of Literature

The Beta function is a unique function where it is classified as the **first kind of Euler's integral**. The Beta function is defined in the domains of real numbers. The notation to represent the beta function is " β ". The beta function is meant by $B(p, q)$, where the parameters p and q should be real numbers. The Beta function was introduced early 19th century. The function was later extensively studied by other mathematicians, including Augustin-Louis Cauchy and Carl Gustav Jacobi, who contributed to understanding its properties and relationship with other mathematical functions.

The Gamma function was first introduced by Swiss mathematician Leonhard Euler in the 18th century although it was later formalized and studied extensively by other mathematicians

Both functions have since been further developed and studied by numerous mathematicians and have found applications in various areas of Mathematics, Physics and engineering. Due to usefulness of these functions Chaudhary and Zubair studied extended Gamma and Beta functions

The Pochhammer symbol, also known as the rising factorial, was named after the German mathematician Leo August Pochhammer. Pochhammer lived from 1841 to 1920 and made significant contributions to various areas of mathematics, including number theory, algebra, and analysis.

The Gauss hypergeometric function ${}_2F_1$ is a special function that plays a fundamental role in many areas of mathematics, physics, and engineering. It is named after the German mathematician Carl Friedrich Gauss. The Gauss hypergeometric function has numerous properties and relationships with other mathematical functions, and its study continues to be an active area of research in mathematics and its applications.

$F_1, F_2, F_3,$ and F_4 are the functions that Appell developed in 1880, now popularly known as Appell functions. These are two variables extension of ${}_2F_1$ function.

Result and Discussion

It is useful here to define the following relations for Pochhammer symbol [10], pp.21-23; eqs. (4), (15),

$$\begin{aligned}
 (18),(20),(24)](a)_n &= \begin{cases} a(a+1)\dots(a+n-1); & \text{if } n=1,2,\dots \\ 1; & \text{if } n=0 \end{cases} \\
 &= \frac{\Gamma(a+n)}{\Gamma(a)} \tag{2.1}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\Gamma(a-n) = \frac{(-1)^n \Gamma(a)}{(1-a)_n} \tag{2.2}$$

$$(\lambda)_{m+n} = (\lambda)_m (\lambda+m)_n \tag{2.3}$$

The duplication formula defined in the following form.

$$(\lambda)_{2n} = 2^{2n} \left(\frac{\lambda}{2}\right)_n \left(\frac{\lambda+1}{2}\right)_n \tag{2.4}$$

The generalized hypergeometric function is defined and represented by the following series [10]

$${}_pF_q \left[\begin{matrix} a_1, \dots, a_p; \\ b_1, \dots, b_q; \end{matrix} z \right] = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{\prod_{i=1}^p (a_i)_n}{\prod_{j=1}^q (b_j)_n n!}, \tag{2.5}$$

$$p, q \in \mathbb{Z}^+; b_j \neq 0, -1, -2, \dots; i = 1, 2, \dots, r$$

The exponential function ${}_0F_0[-, -; Z]$ and the Gauss's hypergeometric function ${}_2F_1[a, b; c; z]$ are special cases of the above hypergeometric function ${}_pF_q[\cdot]$

The following integrals are also required ([9, p.223], see also [11] and [12])

$$\int_0^1 t^{\alpha-1} (1-t)^{\beta-1} (1-x_1 t)^{-\alpha_1} (1-x_2 t)^{-\alpha_2} dt = B(\alpha, \beta) F_1[\alpha, \alpha_1, \alpha_2; \alpha + \beta; x_1, x_2]$$

$$(\text{Re}(\alpha) > 0, \text{Re}(\beta) > 0; |x_1|, |x_2| < 1) \tag{2.6}$$

Where F_1 is the Appell's double hypergeometric series defined as follows. [11], [12]

$$\int_0^1 t^{\alpha-1} (1-t)^{\beta-1} (1-x_1 t)^{-\alpha_1} (1-x_2 (1-t))^{-\alpha_2} dt = B(\alpha, \beta) F_3[\alpha, \beta, \alpha_1, \alpha_2; \alpha + \beta; x_1, x_2]$$

$$(\operatorname{Re}(\alpha) > 0, \operatorname{Re}(\beta) > 0; |x_1|, |x_2| < 1) \tag{2.7}$$

Where F_3 is Appell's another double hypergeometric series. [11], [12]

$$\int_a^b (t-a)^{\alpha-1} (b-t)^{\beta-1} (ut+v)^\gamma dt$$

$$= B(\alpha, \beta) (b-a)^{\alpha+\beta-1} (au+v)^\gamma {}_2F_1\left[\alpha, -\gamma; \alpha + \beta; \frac{-(b-a)u}{(au+v)}\right] \tag{2.8}$$

$$\operatorname{Re}(\alpha) > 0, \operatorname{Re}(\beta) > 0, \left| \arg\left(\frac{bu+v}{au+v}\right) \right| < \pi$$

Main Result

In this section we will study the following general class of integrals in view of the series integral representation of extended Beta function in (1.7)

$$(i) \quad I_{A, \alpha, \beta, \gamma; \lambda_1, p_1, \dots, \lambda_r, p_r; a, b} [\phi(t), \psi(t)]$$

$$= \frac{1}{B(\alpha, \beta)} \int_a^b (t-a)^{\alpha-1} (b-t)^{\beta-1} [\phi(t)]^\gamma \exp[-A\psi(t)] \prod_{i=1}^r [1 - \exp(-p_i \psi(t))]^{\lambda_i} dt$$

$$(3.1)$$

$$\operatorname{Re}(\alpha), \operatorname{Re}(\beta), \operatorname{Re}(A) > 0 \quad \lambda_i, p_i > 0 \text{ for } i = 1, 2, \dots, r$$

EVALUATION OF INTEGRALS: -

The following three integrals are evaluated for certain values of the particular functions $\phi(t), \psi(t)$ and $f(t)$ in our main general class of integrals considered in (3.1)

Integral-1

For $\phi(t) = (1-x_1 t)^{-\alpha_1} (1-x_2 t)^{-\alpha_2}$ $\psi(t) = \frac{1}{t(1-t)}$, $a = 0$ and $b = \gamma = 1$

We have

$${}_2F_2 \left[\begin{matrix} \frac{(1-\alpha-\beta-m_1)}{2}, \frac{(2-\alpha-\beta-m_1)}{2} \\ (1-\beta), (1-\alpha-m_1) \end{matrix} ; \frac{-4 \left(A + \sum_{i=1}^r p_i n_i \right)}{(b-a)^2} \right] \quad (3.4)$$

Where $\text{Re}(\alpha), \text{Re}(\beta) > 0, \left| \arg \left(\frac{bu+v}{au+v} \right) \right| < \pi, a \neq b$ and the result in (3.4) exists.

OUT LINE OF PROOFS:

Proof of (3.2)

To prove the result in (3.2) we denote its left-hand side by Δ_1 i.e.

$$\Delta_1 = I_{A, \alpha, \beta, \lambda_1, p_1, \dots, \lambda_r, p_r; 0,1} \left[(1-x_1 t)^{-\alpha_1} (1-x_2 t)^{-\alpha_2}, \frac{1}{t(1-t)} \right]$$

Now in view of the general notation of class of integrals (3.1) we have the following form of integral.

$$\Delta_1 = \frac{1}{B(\alpha, \beta)} \int_0^1 t^{\alpha-1} (1-t)^{\beta-1} (1-x_1 t)^{-\alpha_1} (1-x_2 t)^{-\alpha_2}.$$

$$\exp \left[-\frac{A}{t(1-t)} \right] \prod_{i=1}^r \left[1 - \exp \left(\frac{-p_i}{t(1-t)} \right) \right]^{\lambda_i} dt$$

Now using binomial expansion and then expressing exponential function in series form ${}_0F_0$ with the help of (2.5) and then changing the order of summation and integration we have

$$\Delta_1 = \frac{1}{B(\alpha, \beta)} \sum_{m, n_1, \dots, n_r=0}^{\infty} \frac{\prod_{i=1}^r [(-\lambda_i)_{n_i}] \left(-A - \sum_{i=1}^r p_i n_i \right)^m}{n_1! \dots n_r! m!} \int_0^1 t^{(\alpha-m)-1} (1-t)^{(\beta-m)-1} (1-x_1 t)^{-\alpha_1} (1-x_2 t)^{-\alpha_2} dt$$

Now on evaluating the inner integral with the help of (2.6) and using their in the definition of Appell function F_1 and then interpreting the m series into ${}_2F_2$ in view of (2.1) to (2.4) and (2.5) we atonce arrived at the desired result in (3.2)

The Results (3.3) and (3.4) are proved following on similar lines as to prove in (3.2) and using (2.7) (2.8) there in respectively.

Conclusion

SPECIAL CASES:

If in (3.2), (3.3) and (3.4), we take $r = 1$ these reduce to the known results due to Pathan, Jaimini and Sharma [9, pp.5-8, Eqs.3.3-3.5] respectively.

If in main result (3.2), (3.3) and (3.4) we take $\lambda = 0$ and $r = 1$ then these reduce immediately to the known results due to Khan et.al [5, pp.1995-1996, eqs. (2.2), (2.4), (2.6)] respectively.

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